

CLIMATE CONDITIONS OF KARAKALPAKSTAN AND FIG CULTIVATION

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Abstract. The article talks about the climatic conditions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and its special weather. Changes in climate and the advantages of growing figs under these conditions are studied. It was said about the cultivation of fruits in an ecological environment.

Key words: Ecological environment, climate, fruit production, figs, weather.

Introduction. The climate of Amiwdayan delta in the entire region of Karakalpakstan is dry, the air is dry, and the winter is cold. The climatic changes of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are characterized by sharp continentality.

For example, in the lower delta of Amiwdayan, the air is hot and dry, there are many hot days, and the daily temperature fluctuates sharply.

It is cold in winter compared to other parts of Uzbekistan.

The amount of moisture of the jaw-eye of this area is 100-110 mm in the back part of the delta. In this case, the hair is not stable, and the hairs are not patched, and they are very little. This region is considered the driest part of Uzbekistan due to the amount of rainfall.

The average air temperature in these areas is 26 C in the summer (July), 28.2 C in the east, and the maximum temperature is 43 C-44 C. The minimum temperature is about 32 C in different seasons. The vegetation period of plants in these regions (temperature above 5 C) is 219-230 days.

Materials and methods. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the continentality of the climate began to decrease from the north to the west. The average moisture content is light, the amount of snow varies from 70 mm to 100 mm. Most of the harvest was in winter and spring months, in spring and summer, there was little rain, and most of the winter snow was in March.

According to the most recent data, the average rainfall in this region is 13 mm, and in April and May, it is 20-25 mm. Due to the early arrival of the spring months, the amount of Nókiste livestock increased significantly in March and April.

Due to the climate of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are separated from each other. The total temperature in Šimbai (back) is 3778, Tórtkúlde (kubla) is 4416, compared to the kubla zone, the vegetation period in the back zone is 13-17 days. The average humidity temperature is 10-12 degrees in the cold months of December and January. The average monthly temperature of January in Shymbai is 7.6 degrees, in Nakhchivan it is 6.9 degrees, and the absolute minimum on the territory of Karakalpakstan is 31 degrees to 35 degrees.

The last frosts in the eastern part of this territory begin on April 20, in the rear part on April 20, and in the rear part on April 23, early autumn frosts begin on October 10 in the rear part and on October 25 in the front part. During severe frosts, the temperature dropped from 1 degree to 5 degrees. In the course of the year, the wind blows at a speed of 15-20 meters in gusts of 2, 4, 8 meters per second.

In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the amount of air pollution has increased. It is between 8.0 and 10.0 mb. In the rainy season, it reaches 12-17 mb, and in winter it drops to 4.6 mb. Havani's comparability is low in jazz, and it has been determined that it is very childish.

Ficus kariyskiy, Latin *Ficus caricatábiyatta*, is a large woody plant and it was called a fig. It is possible to bring it to the shape of the room. In order to get fruit in the greenhouse, it is necessary to choose varieties that are easy to grow. The fig tree is a single-headed and double-headed milkweed. The flowers of the erkek ham rose like a pear in the hole in the neck of the topgüldin.

The seed-bearing blastophaga (*Balstophaga grossarum*) is a small herbaceous plant. After spawning, each female's tuft turns into a small fruit, and the petals of the top flower turn into juicy and tasty figs.

Cultivation of the fig tree. It is recommended to use it in the room with a lot of power. Temperature: 28-32 oC in winter, 5-10 oC during a short rest period.

It is necessary to water frequently during the day of watering, as the reason for this is that it is a sweet plant. In the winter time, the suddi does not demand so much, but it was able to maintain its efficiency. Havani's resistance - this plant needs to be watered more often. Fertilization - it is advisable to fertilize with organic matter in the form of biophumus throughout the year. In early spring, it is better to use complex fertilizers for fruiting plants. You need to mix and match the different colors. Al, it is possible to replace the surface on the top of the large shells.

This is why uniforms are cut off during the rainy season. *Ficus carica* really likes me. This plant is a large, bushy plant with a woody stem, and its height is 5-12 meters. The scales are large and small. The leaves are 3-5 claw-like. The flowers are ball-shaped and pear-shaped. In nature, Kishi is widely distributed in Asia, India, and the Mediterranean Sea. 4,000 years ago, the bride was bowed down.

The fig tree goes through a period of winter dormancy, and the leaves drop even when the temperature drops. Its juicy fruit is marked as fig fruit or wine fruit, and is given in table #1 below.

Among the species of ficus, this plant is said to be the most popular. In the living room, when the mirror is close to the sunlight, it grows faster. If a lot of watering is required in the spring season, then in the winter season, less watering is required. It is necessary to cut the stems at the end of the vegetation for better growth.

According to the literature, it is better to keep it in a cool place at a temperature of 10 C. The fact that the fig plant is different from other plants makes me sick. Everyone loves me during the jazz season

Ficus carica is a subtropical fruit tree, grows up to 8 meters high and bears 2 fruits in one season. Like other plants of the *Ficus* genus, it produces white milky juices in the leaf tissues. The leaves of this plant are large, the lower leaves are smooth, and the leaves are heart-like. The lower side of the leaf is covered with small spots and the side of the alder has a light green color. Jas is a good boy. Ánjirdi produced two types of bullets. Female flowers in one tube and male flowers in the other tuber are attached to short flower stalks. *Ficus kariyskiy*, Latin *Ficus caricatábiyatta*, is a large woody plant and it was called a fig. It is possible to bring it to the shape of the room. In order to get fruit in the greenhouse, it is necessary to choose varieties that are easy to grow. The fig tree is a single-headed and double-headed milkweed. The flowers of the erkek ham rose like a pear in the hole in the neck of the topgüldin.

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Results and discussion. In the winter time, the suddi does not demand so much, but it was able to maintain its efficiency. Havani's resistance - this plant needs to be watered more often. Fertilization - it is advisable to fertilize with organic matter in the form of biophumus throughout the year. In early spring, it is better to use complex fertilizers for fruiting plants. You need to mix and match the different colors. Al, it is possible to replace the surface on the top of the large shells.

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Conclusion. *Ficus carica* is a subtropical fruit tree, grows up to 8 meters high and bears 2 fruits in one season. Like other plants of the *Ficus* genus, it produces white milky juices in the leaf tissues. The leaves of this plant are large, the lower leaves are smooth, and the leaves are heart-like. The lower side of the leaf is covered with small spots and the side of the alder has a light green color. Jas is a good boy. *Ficus* produced two types of bullets. Female flowers in one tube and male flowers in the other tuber are attached to short flower stalks.

References

1. Burigin V.A., Jongurazov F.X. Botanika Toshkent "Óqituvchi" 1977
2. Джон Марк-Брайт. Все лучшие комнатные растения. Москва ЗАО «Фитон+» 2006. 175 С
3. Забаровский Е.П. Плоды И семена древесных И кустарниковых пород. М., 1962.
4. Kosnazarov K.A., Atamuratov R., Rametov A.K. Tut ósimligi hám oniń áhmiyeti. Материали республиканской научно-практической конференции. "Рациональное использование природных ресурсов Ўжноги Приарала" Нукус-2012.-25-26 Б.